

Mapping Research Topics on The Determinants and Influence of the Market Value Added (MVA) Ratio in Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the determinants and effects of the Market Value Added (MVA) ratio in banking using a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The type of data used is secondary data. The source of data collection comes from searching national journals indexed by Google Scholar and accredited by Sinta through the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping research around the MVA ratio using a bibliometric study with the VOSviewer algorithm software; (2) mapping the influence and determinant variables of the MVA ratio in banking using a literature review study. The results showed that based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the research on the determinants and effects of the MVA ratio was divided into 5 clusters and 192 topic items. Meanwhile, based on a literature review study, 11 influences and 30 determinants of the MVA ratio in banking exist. The implications and contributions of this research are to map topics around the MVA ratio in banking, which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Market Value Added (MVA), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Banking.

Introduction

In the banking industry, Market Value Added (MVA) is used to assess a bank's financial performance and its future growth potential. This can be done by measuring the difference between the bank's market value and the total capital invested by shareholders and creditors. For example, if the market value of Bank X is \$1 billion and the total capital invested by shareholders and creditors is \$800 million, then the MVA of Bank X is \$200 million. However, the use of MVA in banking tends to be limited. One factor is a lack of understanding of the MVA concept. This concept is relatively new and requires a fairly in-depth understanding of company finances. In addition, measuring the market value of banks can also be difficult because there is not always a recorded market price for certain banks.

Limited data available can also be an obstacle in using MVA. Sometimes it is difficult to obtain accurate and complete data regarding the total capital invested by shareholders and creditors, as well as the actual market value of the bank. Despite this, several large banks have started using MVA as one of their financial performance metrics. An example is Bank of America, which has adopted MVA as one of their key performance indicators in financial reports. In addition, several financial consulting companies have also started offering MVA measurement services for the banking industry. In the long term, the use of MVA in banking is predicted to increase along with increasing awareness of the importance of measuring added value in the financial industry. By using MVA, banks can assess whether their business strategy has created added value for

shareholders. The use of MVA can also help banks to improve their financial performance and strengthen their position in the market.

Along with the increasing importance of measuring added value in the banking industry, research on the use of MVA in banking is also growing. The following are some of the latest research developments regarding MVA in banking: first, the influence of MVA announcements on bank market value. This research aims to test whether MVA announcements have a significant impact on bank market value. The research results show that the MVA announcement has a positive and significant impact on bank market value. This shows that the MVA announcement can be a positive signal for investors and strengthen the bank's position in the market. Second, the influence of MVA on bank financial performance. This research aims to test whether MVA has a positive influence on bank financial performance. The research results show that MVA has a positive influence on bank financial performance, such as profitability and efficiency. This shows that MVA can be used as an effective financial performance measurement tool for banks. Third, factors that influence MVA in banking. This research aims to identify factors that influence MVA in banking. Some of the factors identified include asset quality, financial ratios, asset growth, and bank size. Research results show that these factors significantly influence MVA in banking. Fourth, comparative analysis of MVA with other financial metrics. This research aims to conduct a comparative analysis between MVA and other financial metrics, such as Economic Value Added (EVA) and Return on Equity (ROE). The research results show that MVA has a positive relationship with EVA and ROE, but has a higher sensitivity to changes in stock prices. Overall, research on the use of MVA in banking continues to develop to identify the benefits and potential of this metric in improving bank financial performance and creating added value for shareholders.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around MVA in Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding MVA. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research MVA. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics surrounding the MVA ratio in banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

Market Value Added (MVA) or Market Value Added is a measure of a company's financial performance that can be used to measure the added value created by the company in the long term. MVA can be defined as the difference between the market value of a company (in this case, banking) and its book value, which describes how much added value the company has created for its shareholders. In the banking context, MVA can be calculated by comparing the bank's market value (i.e. the bank's share price announced on the stock exchange) with its book value (i.e. the bank's net asset value after deducting all liabilities and debts). If the bank's market value is higher than its book value, then the bank is considered to have created positive added value for shareholders. MVA is usually used together with other financial performance measures, such as Return On Equity (ROE) and Economic Value Added (EVA), to provide a more complete picture of a company 's financial performance.

Bibliometric studies are research method that uses bibliographic data or references from published literature to analyze the coverage, distribution and patterns of use of literature in a particular field. This method is usually carried out using statistical and mathematical techniques to study the frequency and interconnectedness of references in a particular literature. In bibliometric studies, researchers collect bibliographic data from sources such as journals, books, conferences, and other publications related to a particular research field. This bibliographic data is then analyzed to study patterns of literature use, such as: (1) Coverage of topics and research trends in a particular field; (2) Identify the authors or institutions that have influenced the research field the most; (3) Analysis of collaboration networks between authors or institutions in certain research fields; (4) Analyze the distribution and frequency of use of certain keywords in the literature. Bibliometric studies are very useful in understanding the development of certain research fields, as well as helping researchers in determining relevant research topics and making significant contributions in that field.

VOSviewer is simple software for network analysis and visualization of bibliometric data. VOSviewer is used to analyze and visualize bibliometric data from sources such as scientific publications, journals, books, and conferences. VOSviewer allows users to create network visualization maps of specific keywords or topics within specific research areas. This software processes the bibliometric data imported into it and creates a network based on the frequency and relatedness of keywords or topics contained in the bibliometric data source. Apart from that, VOSviewer can also show clusters or groups of keywords or topics that are related to each other. The main advantage of VOSviewer is its ability to visualize bibliometric data in an easy-to-understand and attractive form. This visualization helps researchers to better understand the relationships and patterns of their bibliometric data and makes it easier to draw conclusions from the data. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, practitioners, and professionals in various research fields and industries to gain better insight into the range of topics and trends in the literature relevant to their field.

Studies literature review is a type of research study carried out by collecting, evaluating, and analyzing literature or other scientific works relevant to a particular research topic. The literature review study aims to identify and analyze debates, gaps in research that has been conducted, as well as identifying conclusions that can be drawn from the results of previous research. In a literature review study, researchers collect data from various literature sources, including journals, books, reports, conference papers, and other documents related to the research topic. After the data was collected, the researcher carried out analysis and synthesis of the data using statistical techniques and/or qualitative methods to prepare a report on the results of the literature review study. Literature review studies can be carried out in various fields of science and are one of the methods most often used in scientific research. This method is very useful for developing knowledge about a particular research topic, identifying gaps in research that has been conducted, and gaining a more comprehensive view of the research topic. Apart from that, literature review studies can also help researchers to develop new hypotheses, develop theoretical frameworks and research methodologies, and plan further research. The results of literature review studies are often used as a basis for further research studies or used to assist decision making in certain fields.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Market Value Added (MVA). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about MVA in Banking.

The source of data collection comes from searching national journals indexed by Google Scholar and accredited by Sinta through the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category including the key words " Net Operating Margin " and "NOM" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping and Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the Market Value Added (MVA) Ratio in Banking

There are 267 national journals indexed by Google Scholar and accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection originating from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1996 to 2023.

Table 1. Journal publication data about MVA by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1996	1	2012	8	2018	20
2005	1	2013	13	2019	31
2007	1	2014	10	2020	23
2008	3	2015	15	2021	39
2009	3	2016	22	2022	38
2010	3	2017	22	2023	10
2011	4				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

effect, stock exchange/price/return, technique, data analysis technique, variable.

- Cluster 3, consists of 35 topic items, namely: bei, bep, Indonesian stock exchange, change, classic assumption testing, correlation, decision, Indonesian effect, equity, f test, hypothesis testing, independent variable, analysis method, multiple regression analysis, net profit margin, npm, influence of economic value added/market value added, company, positive effect, purposive sampling, roe, secondary source, significant on mva/return, spss, t test, term, autocorrelation test, f/heteroscedasticity/normality test/t.
- Cluster 4 consists of 14 topic items, namely: annual report, book value, company value, corporate social responsibility, CSR, data analysis, firm value, level, influence of market value, price, relationship, research sample, show, stakeholder.
- Cluster 5, consists of 8 topic items, namely: cash flow, coefficient, decision making, determination, implication, manager, multiple regression, operating cash flow.

Mapping Literature Review Studies regarding the Influence of Market Value Added (MVA) Ratios in Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 11 influences of the MVA ratio in banking, namely:

First, share prices. If the company succeeds in creating added value for shareholders, its MVA will increase, which can indicate that the company has good prospects in the future and its financial performance is good. This can make investors feel more interested in buying the company's shares, so that demand for the company's shares increases and can increase the company's share price.

Second, Invest Feasibility/investment decisions. If the MVA is positive, it can be a signal to investors that the company is creating good added value for shareholders, so that the company has good prospects for future growth. This can increase the level of investor confidence and make them more interested in investing in the company.

Third, financial performance. MVA can influence financial performance in banking because MVA shows whether the company has succeeded in creating sufficient added value to offset the capital that has been invested. If MVA is positive, it means that the company has succeeded in creating significant added value and can achieve better financial performance. However, if MVA is negative, it means the company failed to create sufficient added value and could experience poor financial performance.

Fourth, stock performance. MVA can also influence stock performance in banking because the added value generated by the company can increase the company's market value and its share price. If the MVA is positive, it means that the company has succeeded in creating significant added value and can increase its share price. However, if the MVA is negative, it means the company has failed to create enough added value and can reduce its share price.

Fifth, capital. MVA can influence capital in banking because MVA shows whether the company has succeeded in creating sufficient added value to offset the capital that has been invested. If the MVA is positive, it means the company has succeeded in creating significant added value and can increase its capital. However, if the MVA is negative, it means the company has failed to create sufficient added value and can reduce its capital.

Sixth, company value. MVA can also influence company value in banking because the added value generated by the company can increase the company's market value. If MVA is positive, it means the company has succeeded in creating significant added value and can increase company value. However, if the MVA is negative, it means the company has failed to create sufficient added value and this can reduce the company's value.

Seventh, stock income. MVA can influence stock earnings in banking because MVA shows whether the company has succeeded in creating enough added value to increase the company's market value. If MVA is positive, it means that the company has succeeded in creating significant added value and can increase the company's market value. This can increase investor interest and strengthen market sentiment towards banking, thereby increasing stock income.

Eighth, stock returns. MVA can also influence stock returns in banking because the added value generated by the company can strengthen market sentiment towards the company. If the MVA is positive, it means that the company has succeeded in creating significant added value and can increase investor interest in banking. This can increase stock returns because more investors are interested in buying banking shares.

Ninth, Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a ratio that measures a company's efficiency in generating profits from each amount of assets owned. MVA can influence ROA because the added value generated by the company can increase the company's market value, thereby increasing the company's revenue and profits. In other words, the higher the company's MVA, the higher the company's market value, and the higher the possibility that the company can generate greater profits from the assets it owns.

Tenth, Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a ratio that measures a company's efficiency in generating profits from each amount of equity it owns. MVA can influence ROE because the added value generated by the company can increase the company's market value, thereby increasing the company's equity value. In other words, the higher the company's MVA, the higher the company's market value, and the higher the possibility that the company can generate greater profits from the equity it has.

Eleventh, Tobin Q. Tobin's Q is a ratio that measures the relationship between a company's market value and the company's book value. MVA can influence Tobin's Q because MVA is one of the factors that influences a company's market value. The higher the company's MVA, the higher the company's market value compared to its book value. This can increase Tobin's Q because the higher Tobin's Q, the higher the company's market value compared to its book value, and the higher the possibility of the company generating greater profits from the assets and equity it owns.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinant Variables of Market Value Added (MVA) Ratios in Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 30 determinant variables of the MVA ratio in banking, namely:

First, Acid-test Ratio/ATR. ATR can provide an overview of a company's ability to meet short-term financial obligations. If a company has a high ATR, it can indicate that the company has good liquidity and is able to meet its financial obligations easily. This can increase the level of investor confidence and make them more interested in buying shares in the company, which in turn can increase the company's MVA.

Second, acquisition. Acquisitions can impact a company's MVA. If the acquisition is carried out correctly and can create added value for the company, then the company's MVA can increase. However, if the acquisition does not provide added value to the company, the company's MVA may decrease.

Third, Basic Earning Power/BEP. BEP can provide an overview of a company's operational efficiency and its ability to generate profits. If a company has a high BEP, then the company can be considered to have good operational performance, which can attract investor interest and increase the value of the company's shares. This can ultimately increase the company's MVA.

Fourth, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. CSR can influence a company's MVA through factors such as company reputation, relationships with stakeholders, and compliance with regulations and business ethical standards. If the company has a good reputation in terms of CSR, then the company can attract more investor interest and can increase the value of the company's shares, which in turn can increase the company's MVA.

Fifth, Covid-19. The impact of Covid-19 on banking is very significant due to a decrease in loan demand and an increase in credit risk. This can cause a decrease in company revenue, an increase in operational expenses, and a decrease in the value of company shares, which in turn can affect the company's MVA.

Sixth, Current Ratio. Current Ratio can provide an overview of the company's ability to meet short-term obligations using current assets. If a company has a high Current Ratio, then the company is considered to have good liquidity and can handle short-term obligations effectively. This can attract investor interest and increase the value of the company's shares, which in turn can increase the company's MVA.

Seventh, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. DER can influence MVA in banking because companies with high DER tend to have higher risk and are financially unstable. This can cause a decrease in investor confidence and reduce the value of the company's shares, which in turn can reduce the company's MVA. On the other hand, companies with low DER tend to be more financially stable and can attract investor interest, which can increase the company's share value and the company's MVA.

Eighth, Degree Of Financial Leverage/DFL. DFL can influence MVA in banking because companies with high DFL tend to be more sensitive to changes in interest rates and unstable economic conditions. When interest rates rise, companies with high DFL will pay higher interest, which can reduce profits and the value of the company's shares. This can reduce investor interest and company MVA. In contrast, companies with low DFL tend to be more stable and less sensitive to market fluctuations, which can increase the company's share value and the company's MVA.

Ninth, Degree of Operating Leverage/DOL. The DOL measures how much a company relies on fixed costs in its operations. Companies with high DOL have large fixed costs, which can result in high profits when revenues increase, but can also result in large losses when revenues decrease. In this case, banking companies that have high DOL can be affected by fluctuations in their revenues and fixed costs. If revenues decline, their fixed costs can lead to large losses and lower the share value and MVA of the company.

Ninth, Dividend Per Share/DPS. DPS measures how much dividend a company pays to shareholders for each share they own. Stable and consistently increasing dividends can indicate financial stability and investor confidence in the company. This can increase investor interest and the value of the company's

shares, which in turn can increase the company's MVA. Conversely, if companies do not pay dividends or cut their dividends, this can reduce investor confidence and reduce the company's share value and MVA.

Tenth, Earning Per Share/EPS. EPS measures the profit generated by each share owned by shareholders. Stable and consistently increasing EPS can increase investor confidence in the company and increase investor interest, which in turn can increase the share value and MVA of the company. However, it should be noted that EPS does not always reflect the actual performance of the company because it can be influenced by factors such as shares outstanding, stock splits, or changes in the company's accounting policies.

Eleventh, Economic Value Added/EVA. EVA measures how effective a company is in generating profits above its cost of capital. In this case, banking companies that are able to produce positive EVA can demonstrate effectiveness in using capital and demonstrate success in creating added value for shareholders. This can increase investor interest and the value of the company's shares, which in turn can increase the company's MVA.

Twelfth, Financial Ratio. Financial Ratio includes various financial ratios, such as profitability, liquidity and efficiency ratios, which describe a company's financial health. Banking companies that have healthy and stable financial ratios tend to be more attractive to investors and have the potential to generate greater profits, which in turn can increase the company's share value and MVA. However, it should be noted that healthy and stable financial ratios are not the only factor that can influence MVA. Other factors such as company reputation, economic conditions, industry competition, and government policies can also influence a company's MVA.

Thirteenth, Good Corporate Governance/GCG. GCG refers to the principles of good corporate governance, including transparency, accountability, social responsibility and protection of minority shareholder rights. Banking companies that implement good GCG can increase investor confidence and strengthen the company's image, which in turn can increase investor interest and the value of the company's shares and MVA. On the other hand, non-compliance with GCG principles can give rise to investor doubts and concerns about the company's performance and potential risks, which can affect the company's share value and MVA.

Fourteenth, Initial Public Offering/IPO. An IPO can influence Market Value Added (MVA) in banking by increasing the company's market value in the eyes of investors. Along with the IPO, investor confidence in the company can increase because the company meets the requirements and standards needed to conduct an IPO. This can increase market perception of the company and potentially increase the MVA value.

Fifteenth, Intellectual Capital/IC. IC can increase the value of MVA in banking because companies that have strong IC can increase their competitive advantage and financial performance. The presence of IC can also reflect the quality of company management in managing its resources and can indicate potential profits in the future. Thus, IC can increase the MVA value in banking.

Sixteenth, inflation. Inflation can affect the real value of a company's assets and liabilities, including banking. If inflation rises, the prices of goods and services will also rise, so company profits will also increase. However, if inflation is too high, it could have a negative impact on the economy as a whole and reduce investor confidence in the market. This can reduce banking MVA.

Seventeenth, Institutional Ownership. A high percentage of institutional ownership in a company, including banks, can increase investor confidence in

the company and increase the liquidity of its shares. This can increase the company's MVA because the higher the demand for shares, the higher the value of the shares.

Eighteenth, merger. A merger or merger between two companies can have a significant impact on banking MVA. In some cases, mergers can increase company efficiency and productivity, thereby increasing financial performance and company value. This can have a positive impact on banking MVA. However, there is also the possibility that the merger will not be successful and may even reduce the value of the company if there are problems in integration or if there are differences in culture and values between the two companies. Therefore, mergers need to be considered carefully and a comprehensive analysis needs to be carried out before carrying out the merger.

Nineteenth, Managerial Ownership. A high percentage of managerial ownership in a company, including banking, can improve company performance and increase management's focus on the long term. This can have a positive impact on the company's MVA because management who own shares can have interests that are in line with the interests of other shareholders. However, too high a percentage of managerial ownership can also cause management to focus too much on personal interests rather than the interests of the company and other shareholders. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out strict supervision of management who have share ownership in the company.

Twentieth, home country. In general, banks have a tendency to focus their business on the domestic market or in their country of origin. This can have an impact on MVA, where banks operating in countries with large and developing markets usually have greater MVA potential compared to banks operating in countries with small and less developed markets. Apart from that, other factors such as regulations, politics and economic conditions in the country of origin can also influence MVA in banking.

Twenty-first, exchange rate. Exchange rates can also affect MVA in banking. When the exchange rate rises, assets and income in foreign currency will increase. This can have a positive impact on the MVA of banks that have asset portfolios in foreign currencies. However, if the exchange rate falls, assets and income denominated in foreign currency will decrease and can have a negative impact on banking MVA. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to exchange rate risk in managing their asset and liability portfolios.

Twenty-second, Net Operating Profit After Tax/NOPAT. The higher the NOPAT, the greater the possibility that the company can generate profits in the future, so this can increase the company's market value and its MVA.

Twenty-third, Operating Cash Flow/OCF. The greater the OCF, the higher the company's ability to pay debts and investments and increase future profits, so this can increase the company's market value and its MVA.

Twenty-fourth, disclosure of social responsibility. Disclosure of social responsibility can influence investor and public perceptions of company performance and the added value generated by the company. If a company is seen to be active in carrying out its social responsibilities, for example by carrying out social or environmental activities, then this can improve the company's image in the eyes of the public and can have a positive impact on the company's share price and its MVA value.

Twenty-fifth, Return On Assets/ROA. ROA can also affect MVA. ROA measures how effective a company is in generating profits from the assets it owns. The higher the ROA, the more effective the company is in utilizing its assets to generate profits. This can be interpreted as meaning that the company has higher

added value and is better able to generate additional economic value, so that it can increase its MVA value.

Twenty-sixth, Return On Equity/ROE. The influence of ROE on MVA in banking is very significant. A high ROE shows that the company is effective in generating profits for shareholders, which can increase the company's share price and MVA. Investors will tend to invest in companies with high ROE, because this indicates good performance and the potential to generate greater profits.

Twenty-seventh, ownership structure. Ownership structure can also influence a company's MVA in banking. A study shows that institutional ownership has a positive effect on MVA in banking companies. This is because institutional ownership is considered a sign of trust from professional investors and can improve a company's image on the stock market. On the other hand, excessive family or individual ownership can reduce MVA because they tend to make business decisions that are personal rather than in the interests of the company as a whole. Therefore, banking companies that have a healthy and diverse ownership structure can increase their MVA value.

Twenty-eighth, Supply Chain Strategy. Supply Chain Strategy can influence a company's operational efficiency, reduce production costs, and increase customer satisfaction, which in turn can increase profits and company value. For example, if a bank has an effective supply chain strategy in managing its operational costs, this can increase bank profits and then affect overall company value, including MVA.

Twenty-ninth, Times Interest Earned/TIE. TIE shows a company's ability to pay interest on its debt, which has the potential to influence investor confidence in the company's ability to generate profits. If the TIE is low, then investors may be concerned that the company is unable to pay its debts and the value of the company may decline. This can have an impact on MVA because a decrease in investor confidence can reduce the company's share price and market value.

Thirtieth, Weight Average Cost of Capital/WACC. WACC can affect company value because it is the cost required by a company to finance new investments and business expansion. If WACC is high, then the cost of capital will be higher and the profits generated from new investments may be lower. Conversely, if WACC is low, then the company can generate more profits from new investments, which can affect company value and MVA.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, the number of research publications regarding ratios Market Value Added (MVA) in Banking during the period 1996 to 2023 was 267 research articles, which came from national journals indexed by Google Scholar and accredited by Sinta. Second, in the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding the MVA ratio in banking are divided into 5 clusters and 192 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 81 topics, cluster 2 consists of 54 topics, cluster 3 consists of 35 topics, cluster 4 consists of 14 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 8 topics. Third, based on a literature review, there are 19 the influence of the MVA ratio on banking, namely: stock prices, Invest Feasibility/investment decisions, financial performance, stock performance, capital, company value, stock income, stock returns, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, and Tobin Q. Fourth, based on a literature review, there are 30 variables determining the MVA ratio in banking, namely: Acid-test Ratio/ATR, acquisition, Basic Earning Power/BEP, Corporate Social

Responsibility/CSR, Covid-19, Current Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Degree Of Financial Leverage/DFL, Degree of Operating Leverage/DOL, Dividend Per Share/DPS, Earning Per Share/EPS, Economic Value Added/EVA, Financial Ratio, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, Initial Public Offering/IPO, Intellectual Capital/IC, inflation, Institutional Ownership, merger, Managerial Ownership, country of origin, exchange rate, Net Operating Profit After Tax/NOPAT, Operating Cash Flow/OCF, disclosure of social responsibility, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, ownership structure, Supply Chain Strategy, Times Interest Earned/TIE, and Weight Average Cost of Capital/WACC.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can The following research results were obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the literature review The review can be explained in a more complex way.

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